

A Note on Geometric Algebra and Neural Networks

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Abstract: This note first explains Clifford's geometric algebra (GA) as a general form of complex and quaternion algebras. Second, this note describes GA neuron as a natural extension of complex neuron. The GA neuron inputs a vector and outputs another vector of any dimension. Next, point with precision is considered using conformal geometric algebra and shows that addition of conformal vectors works well for precision update. The GA neuron and its use of vectors with precision (or belief) could be useful to datasets with different levels of precision/details/belief of any dimension. The conformal vector could be also useful to set a prior distribution of geometric versors.

1 Introduction

Let $T(L)$ be the tensor space of the linear vector space L . Grassmann's exterior algebra $E(L)$ regards all elements of $T(L)$ which contain tensor products of any $x \in L$ with x itself as the zero element of $T(L)$. The exterior product or wedge product maps an ordered pair $E(L) \times E(L)$ to $E(L)$. The exterior product is bilinear and $x \wedge x$ becomes 0 for any x in L . Because $0 = (x + y) \wedge (x + y) = x \wedge x + x \wedge y + y \wedge x + y \wedge y$ where x and y are both elements of L , the exterior product is anti-commutative $x \wedge y = -y \wedge x$.

Clifford's geometric algebra $G(L)$ is the exterior algebra of a linear space L equipped with a measure $x \cdot x = |x|^2$. $G(L)$ has a bilinear and associative product, that maps an ordered pair $G(L) \times G(L)$ to $G(L)$, which is called geometric product or Clifford product. For $x, y \in L$, the geometric product (simply written by juxtaposition of the elements) is defined as $xy = x \cdot y + x \wedge y$. Example: Let us think about the 2-dimensional Euclidean space \mathbf{R}^2 . The geometric products of its orthonormal basis vectors $\{e_1, e_2\}$ are $e_1e_1 = e_1 \cdot e_1 = e_2e_2 = e_2 \cdot e_2 = 1$ and $e_1e_2 = e_1 \wedge e_2 = -e_2 \wedge e_1 = -e_2e_1$. Because of the associativity we have $(e_1e_2)^2 = -e_2e_1e_1e_2 = -e_2e_2 = -1$. We therefore denote the unit bivector as $i = e_1e_2$, then $i^2 = -1$. The set of real linear combinations of $\{1, i\}$ is the even grade subalgebra of $G(\mathbf{R}^2)$, which is isomorphic to the set of complex numbers \mathbb{C} .

The authors have naturally extended the complex-valued neuron, all of whose input, weight, bias and output are in \mathbb{C} . The proposed neuron uses the so-called Clifford group $= \{s \in G(L) \mid \varphi(s, x) \in L \forall x \in L\}$, where φ is a function constructed with geometric products, with weight in $G(L)$, and with input, output and bias in L . This note discusses relationship of GA neuron with complex and quaternion neurons. This note also considers points with precision using conformal geometric algebra.

2 Complex Neuron

The complex neuron in general sums input stimuli weighted by weights plus bias complex number. For simplicity, assume the neuron has an input:

$$u_{\mathbb{C}} = w_{\mathbb{C}}x_{\mathbb{C}} + b_{\mathbb{C}},$$

where $u_{\mathbb{C}}, w_{\mathbb{C}}, x_{\mathbb{C}}, b_{\mathbb{C}} \in \mathbb{C}$. A two-dimensional vector (x_1, x_2) can be represented as a complex number. First and second components are put into the real and the imaginary coefficients respectively: $x_{\mathbb{C}} = x_1 + x_2i \in \mathbb{C}$. On the other hand, a natural representation of a vector is $x = x_1e_1 + x_2e_2$. Using geometric algebra $G(\mathbf{R}^2)$, we can link it to the complex number representation as $x_{\mathbb{C}} = x_1(e_1e_1) + x_2(e_1e_2) = e_1(x_1e_1 + x_2e_2) = e_1x$. The square root of $w_{\mathbb{C}} = \rho(\cos \theta + i \sin \theta)$, $\rho \in [0, \infty)$, $\theta \in [0, 2\pi)$ is also a complex number $w'_{\mathbb{C}} = \sqrt{w_{\mathbb{C}}} = \sqrt{\rho}(\cos \frac{\theta}{2} + i \sin \frac{\theta}{2})$. And complex numbers are commutative, i.e. $w'_{\mathbb{C}}(e_1x) = (e_1x)w'_{\mathbb{C}}$. Then, the complex neuron becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} (e_1u) &= w'_{\mathbb{C}}w'_{\mathbb{C}}(e_1x) + (e_1b) \\ &= w'_{\mathbb{C}}(e_1x)w'_{\mathbb{C}} + (e_1b). \end{aligned}$$

Multiply e_1 from the left:

$$e_1e_1u = e_1\underline{w'_{\mathbb{C}}}e_1xw'_{\mathbb{C}} + e_1e_1b.$$

Looking at the underlined part, and let $w'_{\mathbb{C}} = \alpha + \beta i$,

$$\begin{aligned} w'_{\mathbb{C}}e_1 &= (\alpha + \beta i)e_1 = \alpha e_1 + \beta e_1e_2e_1 \\ &= e_1(\alpha - \beta i) = e_1\overline{w'_{\mathbb{C}}}, \end{aligned}$$

where $\overline{w'_{\mathbb{C}}}$ is the conjugation. Then, the complex neuron is represented as:

$$\begin{aligned} e_1e_1u &= e_1e_1\underline{w'_{\mathbb{C}}}xw'_{\mathbb{C}} + e_1e_1b \\ u &= \overline{w'_{\mathbb{C}}}xw'_{\mathbb{C}} + b. \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

This u is the result of rotating x by angle θ with scaling by factor ρ and translation by a vector b .

3 Geometric Algebra Neuron

Geometric algebra neuron is a natural extension of complex neuron. Let Clifford group $\Sigma = \{s \in G(L) \mid \varphi(s, x) \in L \forall x \in L\}$, whose element transforms a vector to another vector. For $k = 0, 1, \dots, n$, the set of versors, i.e. multiplications of k linearly independent vectors $\{M_k = v_1 v_2 \dots v_k \in G(L) \mid v_1, \dots, v_k \in L\}$ is a subset of Σ with $\varphi(M_k, x) = \overline{M_k} x M_k$. The authors have proposed a geometric algebra neuron:

$$u = \sum_{k=0}^n \varphi(M_k, x) + b$$

and found optimal learning rate based on Hessian matrix. Note that the complex neuron of eq. (1) only considers $\varphi(M_2, x)$ part. In the case of $n = 2$, $\varphi(M_0, x)$ is scalar multiplication, $\varphi(M_1, x)$ is reflection, and $\varphi(M_2, x)$ is rotation. These three transformations are mixed. The mixing weights are adjusted as the norm $|M_k|^2$. In the case of $n = 3$, $\varphi(M_2, x)$ is isomorphic to the quaternion product which gives rotation and scaling in three-dimensional space.

4 Conformal GA and Update of Precision

Introducing new two basis vectors $e_+^{\vec{}}$ and $e_-^{\vec{}}$ to $G(\mathbb{R}^n) = G(n)$, we have conformal geometric algebra $G(n+1, 1)$. The new vectors have positive and negative signature, i.e. $e_+^{\vec{2}} = -e_-^{\vec{2}} = 1$. And further new basis vectors are constructed on the $e_+^{\vec{}} \wedge e_-^{\vec{}}$ plane:

$$\begin{cases} n_\infty^{\vec{}} = e_+^{\vec{}} + e_-^{\vec{}} \\ n_o^{\vec{}} = \frac{1}{2}(e_-^{\vec{}} - e_+^{\vec{}}) \end{cases}$$

Because $|n_\infty^{\vec{}}| = |n_o^{\vec{}}| = 0$, they are also called null basis vectors. Using these null basis vectors, n -dimensional hypersphere with center at $\vec{x} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and radius $\rho \in \mathbb{R}$ is represented as

$$X = \mu \vec{x} + \frac{\mu}{2} (\vec{x}^2 - \rho^2) n_\infty^{\vec{}} + \mu n_o^{\vec{}}$$

where μ is any nonzero real number.

We regard ρ^2 of the conformal vector as precision, say $\rho^2 = \beta = \sigma^{-2}$, where σ represents standard deviation. In this interpretation, addition of two conformal vectors means:

$$\begin{aligned} X + Y &= \vec{x} + \vec{y} + \frac{1}{2} (\vec{x}^2 - \beta_x + \vec{y}^2 - \beta_y) n_\infty^{\vec{}} + 2n_o^{\vec{}} \\ &\propto \frac{\vec{x} + \vec{y}}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\vec{x}^2 + \vec{y}^2}{2} - \frac{\beta_x + \beta_y}{2} \right) n_\infty^{\vec{}} + n_o^{\vec{}} \\ &= \vec{m} + \frac{1}{2} (\vec{m}^2 - \beta) n_\infty^{\vec{}} + n_o^{\vec{}} \end{aligned}$$

where $\vec{m} = (\vec{x} + \vec{y})/2$, i.e. the midpoint, and $\beta = (\beta_x + \beta_y)/2 - \{(\vec{x} - \vec{m})^2 + (\vec{y} - \vec{m})^2\}/2$. The new precision β is interpreted as average precision minus variance.

This can be generalized to weighted point. Let $\mu_x \in \mathbb{R}$ be the weight.

$$X = \mu_x \vec{x} + \frac{\mu_x}{2} (\vec{x}^2 - \beta_x) n_\infty^{\vec{}} + \mu_x n_o^{\vec{}}$$

Addition of weighted points is:

$$\begin{aligned} X + Y &= \mu_x \vec{x} + \mu_y \vec{y} + \frac{\mu_x (\vec{x}^2 - \beta_x) + \mu_y (\vec{y}^2 - \beta_y)}{2} n_\infty^{\vec{}} \\ &+ (\mu_x + \mu_y) n_o^{\vec{}} \\ &= \mu \vec{m} + \frac{\mu}{2} (\vec{m}^2 - \beta) n_\infty^{\vec{}} + \mu n_o^{\vec{}} \end{aligned}$$

where $\mu = \mu_x + \mu_y$ is the new weight and

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{m} &= \frac{\mu_x \vec{x} + \mu_y \vec{y}}{\mu} \\ \beta &= \frac{\mu_x \beta_x + \mu_y \beta_y}{\mu} - \frac{\mu_x (\vec{x} - \vec{m})^2 + \mu_y (\vec{y} - \vec{m})^2}{\mu} \end{aligned}$$

\vec{m} is the internally dividing point and the new precision β is interpreted as weighted average precision minus weighted variance.

This fact of good update of precision can be useful to the following cases.

1. Each training/test sample has different levels of precision β (or belief).
2. Massive samples must be learnt and coarse graining is effective. Here, a lot of samples is learnt at once as a hypersphere sample.
3. Precision (or belief) characterises a prior distribution of dataset and neuron parameters.

5 Conclusion

This note described GA neuron as a natural extension of complex neuron. The GA neuron inputs a vector and outputs another vector of any dimension. Next, point with precision was considered using conformal geometric algebra. And we showed that addition of conformal vectors works well to update precision. We want to point out possibility of GA neuron combined with conformal representation of precision in analysis/learning of datasets with various levels of details and in the coarse graining of huge datasets. Bayesian update of weights could also be represented by conformal vectors.

References

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